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Reinventing Scientific Journals through Open Science Practices and Self-Publication

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Abstract

This essay examines strategies to amplify the integrity, inclusivity, and impact of scientific research. Highlighting the importance of addressing the reproducibility crisis and championing open science, it introduces the innovative concept of Self-Publishing Journals (SPJs) to transform traditional scientific publication. The work also presents the 'iko' metric, emphasizing both research dissemination and collaboration. By exploring alternate scientific foundations, the essay underscores the potential of collaborative, transparent, and adaptive scientific approaches for future breakthroughs.

keywords: open science, reproducibility crisis, citizen science, open access publishing, transparent peer review, preprint repositories, self-publishing journals, quality control, iko metric

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Introduction

1. [1–3]
2. The current landscape of scientific publishing calls for a disruption between the publication of scientific articles and quality control agencies.
3. In this essay, we propose the development of Self-Publication Journals (SPJs) as a solution.
4. In a SPJ, the author and the editor are the same person, streamlining the publication process.
5. Scientific papers are valuable sources of knowledge and empowerment, generated by researchers.
6. However, paywall journals restrict free open access to this knowledge.
7. There is an urgent need to upgrade the publishing system to fully incorporate the potential of digital technology.
8. Unfortunately, traditional journals do not meet all the technological demands of academic publishing.
9. Therefore, considering the importance of scientific papers and the limitations of paywall and traditional journals, we propose reinventing scientific journals through self-publication, a concept inspired by self-publishing in the book industry.

Empowering Researchers with Personalized Overlay Journals: A Modern Approach to Scientific Publishing

10. We propose that each researcher can create and operate their own self-publishing scientific journal.
11. This approach offers a modern and robust alternative to the current publishing system of scientific knowledge, exemplified by the Overlay Journal model.
12. An overlay journal is a type of scholarly journal that exists alongside traditional print or electronic journals and provides an alternative means of organizing, reviewing, and publishing academic research.
13. Overlay journals do not host the articles themselves, but instead, they rely on articles that are already available on open-access repositories, such as arXiv.
14. The overlay journal model involves the following steps:
 - a.* Authors submit their preprints to an open-access repository.
 - b.* The overlay journal identifies relevant articles in the repository and invites authors to submit their work for consideration.
 - c.* The submitted articles undergo a peer-review process managed by the overlay journal.
 - d.* If accepted, the articles are officially published in the overlay journal, with links pointing to the original preprint versions hosted in the repository.
15. This model offers several advantages, such as reduced costs for authors and institutions, faster publication times, and it also promotes open access to research, making it more accessible to a wider audience.

Post-Publication Review and Collaborative Authorship: A Novel Approach to Enhancing Research Quality

16. In this proposal, we consider publication to be independent of peer review.
17. Instead, review can take place post-publication.
18. Additionally, the author can issue an open invitation for new collaborators to co-author any paper published in a post-publication review journal.
19. This approach encourages extensive collaboration, which in turn increases the quality of the papers produced.
20. Reviewers can also be invited to co-author the papers they are reviewing.

Quality Control in Self-Publishing: The Role of Quality Standards Committee Agencies

21. A Quality Standards Committee Agency (QCA) would rank the Self-Publishing Journals (SPJs) to ensure quality control.
22. This arrangement separates the publishing institution from the quality control agency, allowing authors to publish what they believe are high-quality papers in their respective SPJs.
23. The quality control agencies will then assess the quality of the papers and the SPJs themselves.

Enhanced Flexibility in Self-Publishing Journals

24. Self-Publishing Journals (SPJs) offer the flexibility to adopt formats tailored for both reader and author convenience.
25. For instance, microarticles present a succinct alternative to traditional scientific articles, utilizing itemized content for efficient knowledge dissemination, enhanced comprehension, and streamlined communication.

Encouraging Researchers to Adopt Self-Publication

26. To persuade researchers to adopt the self-publication model, we propose the following guidelines that would bolster the SPJ system of academic publishing:
 - a.* Establish your own overlay journal.
 - b.* Publish high-quality papers in your SPJ, showcasing a dedication to generating valuable scientific content.
 - c.* Emphasize that the substance of a publication (i.e., “what” is published) holds greater importance than the venue (i.e., “where” it is published).
 - d.* Highlight that self-publication offers researchers the flexibility to share their findings on any platform and in any format.
 - e.* Draw upon examples of job stability in some countries, where university-employed researchers have secure positions, demonstrating that self-publication can flourish in supportive environments.
 - f.* Use the top-quality papers published in SPJs to convince funders and stakeholders that this system is a credible and dependable

approach to academic publishing.

g. Acknowledge the vital role peer review plays in influencing which research projects secure funding.

27. Building the credibility of self-publishing journals (SPJs) among our peers as reliable sources of high-quality papers can solidify the self-publication model as an effective method for generating and disseminating scientific knowledge.

Revolutionizing Scientific Communication with Discretized Publications: Granularity, Modularity, and Dynamic Research for Enhanced Collaboration and Discoverability

28. Discretization in scientific publications refers to the idea of breaking down publications into smaller, more manageable units.

29. In this context, we consider the item as the minimum unit of a scientific publication.

30. This concept has the potential to revolutionize the way scientific findings are communicated, evaluated, and built upon.

31. By adopting this premise, we can envision several benefits and changes in the scientific publication landscape:

a. Increased Granularity: Discretizing publications into smaller units allows for greater granularity in presenting and evaluating research. This can improve the accuracy, specificity, and reproducibility of published findings, as well as facilitate more precise communication between researchers.

b. Modular Research: Breaking down publications into items promotes the idea of modular research, where different components

of a study can be independently reviewed, critiqued, and expanded upon. This can lead to a more efficient and collaborative research process, as researchers can more easily identify and address specific aspects of a study.

- c.* **Dynamic Publications:** Discretized publications can be continuously updated and revised based on new findings, feedback, and post-publication peer review. This creates a more dynamic and iterative approach to research evaluation and communication, ensuring that published findings remain accurate, current, and useful.
- d.* **Alternative Metrics:** Evaluating research based on individual items rather than entire publications can help shift the focus to the quality and impact of specific findings, rather than relying solely on broader metrics like publication counts or journal impact factors. This can lead to a more fair and accurate assessment of a researcher's contributions.
- e.* **Improved Discoverability:** Breaking down publications into smaller units can improve the discoverability of research findings, as search engines and databases can index and categorize items based on their specific content and context. This can help researchers more easily find relevant information and deepen prior knowledge.
- f.* **Enhanced Collaboration:** Discretized publications can facilitate collaboration between researchers by making it easier to identify and integrate specific findings, methods, or data from other studies. This can promote interdisciplinary research and foster a more efficient and collaborative research ecosystem.

Harnessing the Power of Microarticles: Efficient Scientific Communication, Collaborative Research, and Inclusive Participation with Scientific White Papers

32. Scientific white papers are a proposal for an alternative publishing format that aims to streamline the process of scientific communication.
33. These papers are shorter and more concise than traditional articles, making them quicker to write, read, review, and publish.
34. Alternatively, a scientific white paper is also referred to as a “microarticle.”
35. Microarticles offer several distinct advantages, including:
 - a.* The capacity for updates even after publication, enabling ongoing enhancement and fine-tuning of the content.
 - b.* A versatile structure, with optional introduction and context sections, as these can often be accessed through internet searches or academic databases.
 - c.* The use of numbered items for presenting each argument, fostering readability and modular comprehension.
 - d.* The opportunity to showcase research at various stages, such as drafts, partial results, conjectures, open questions, or unique insights.
 - e.* Alignment with the Open Science paradigm, allowing for an unlimited number of authors or contributors.
 - f.* Inclusivity, as anyone can participate and co-author, embodying the principles of Citizen Science.
 - g.* An open reviewing and peer-reviewing process, promoting involvement from a diverse array of citizen scientists.

- h.* Encouraging reviewers to co-author the article if they make at least one significant contribution to the text, beyond vocabulary, grammar, or spelling corrections.
- 36. By adopting the microarticle (whitepaper) format and its associated features, scientific journals can create a more open, collaborative, and efficient publishing environment.
- 37. This model encourages rapid dissemination of knowledge, interdisciplinary research, and broad participation from the scientific community and beyond.

The Iko System

- 38. The **Iko Metric System (IMS)** is a proposed quantitative measure of scientific success that emphasizes a discretized and collaborative approach to science.
- 39. The term “iko” is derived from a Japanese verb that means progression in an action or situation.
- 40. A simple quantitative metric (SQM) can be devised as the product of two components: the total number of scientific items published by the researcher (represented by i) and the total number of co-authors they have collaborated with (represented by c).
- 41. In this metric, each co-author in a published paper contributes one unit to the score, as does each published scientific item.
- 42. This approach provides a straightforward way to evaluate a researcher’s collaborative efforts and productivity in terms of published scientific items.
- 43. A scientific item, in this context, refers to a single idea typically expressed in one sentence.

44. The IMS is designed to promote collaboration and the publication of concise, focused research findings, fostering a more efficient and accessible scientific process.

Improving Science for Greater Impact and Inclusivity

45. While the current practice of science has been remarkably successful in advancing our understanding of the natural world and driving technological innovation, there are areas where improvements can be made, or alternative approaches could be considered.

46. Some significant elements that could make science more effective or different include:

- a.* Addressing the Reproducibility Crisis: Ensuring the reproducibility of scientific findings is essential for the credibility of research. Addressing issues like publication bias, p-hacking (the practice of manipulating or “tuning” statistical analyses), and inadequate reporting of methods can enhance the reliability and integrity of scientific research.
- b.* Promoting Open Science: Greater emphasis on open access, data sharing, and collaborative platforms can accelerate scientific progress, improve transparency, and foster interdisciplinary research. Open science practices can also reduce redundant efforts and promote efficient use of resources.
- c.* Encouraging Long-term Thinking: Promoting research that emphasizes the long-term consequences, such as in foundational science, and anticipates future challenges can help society prepare for and adapt to changing conditions and emerging issues.
- d.* Supporting High-risk, High-reward Research: Current funding structures often favor incremental research over high-risk, high-reward projects that could lead to groundbreaking discoveries.

Encouraging funding agencies to allocate resources for innovative, high-risk research can potentially transform entire fields.

- e.* Embracing Citizen Science: Involving the public in scientific research can help gather data on a larger scale, increase public understanding of science, and engage people in addressing open problems. Citizen science initiatives can democratize the scientific process and lead to novel insights.
- f.* Encouraging Transdisciplinary Research: Promoting research that transcends traditional disciplinary boundaries can help address complex, multifaceted problems by integrating insights from various fields. Transdisciplinary research can lead to innovative solutions that are not achievable through a single-discipline approach.
- g.* Balancing Specialization and Generalization: While specialization allows researchers to delve deeply into specific areas, fostering a balance between specialization and generalization can promote cross-pollination of ideas, better communication between disciplines, and a more comprehensive understanding of complex problems.
- h.* Collaborating over Competing: Both open science and open culture emphasize collaboration and the exchange of ideas, stimulating a more cooperative and interdisciplinary research environment.

Bridging Boundaries: The Fusion of Open Science and Effective Scientific Communication

- 47. Numerous modifications to institutions, journals, and scientific communication approaches can enhance the effectiveness and equity of science.
- 48. Some potential changes include:

- a.* Open Access Publishing: Encourage journals to adopt open access models, making research articles freely available to anyone, regardless of their affiliation or ability to pay.
- b.* Transparent Peer Review: Promote transparency in the peer-review process by disclosing reviewers' identities and publishing their reports alongside the articles. This can help reduce bias and improve the quality of reviews.
- c.* Preprint Repositories: Support the use of preprint repositories, where researchers can share their manuscripts before they are peer-reviewed and published. This can speed up the dissemination of research findings and facilitate collaboration among scientists.
- d.* Post-publication Review: Identify and correct mistakes, promoting a more dynamic and iterative approach to research evaluation.
- e.* Reproducibility Initiatives: Encourage institutions and journals to prioritize reproducibility by requiring authors to share their data, methods, and code, as well as to conduct replication studies to verify the robustness of published findings.
- f.* Inclusive Authorship and Citation Practices: Adopting guidelines that promote inclusive authorship and citation practices can ensure that all contributors are recognized fairly and that researchers from diverse backgrounds are acknowledged for their work.
- g.* Diversifying Funding Sources: Advocate for a variety of funding sources to support researchers from underrepresented groups and those engaged in unconventional or high-risk projects.
- h.* Reducing Publication Bias: Encourage journals to publish not only positive and novel results but also negative or null findings, as well as replication studies, to help build a more accurate picture of the scientific landscape.
- i.* Rewarding Quality over Quantity: Shift the focus from the num-

- ber of publications to the quality and impact of research in evaluating researchers for funding, promotion, and tenure decisions.
- j.* Collaboration and Interdisciplinary Research: Boost collaboration and interdisciplinary research by creating platforms and funding opportunities that bring together researchers from different fields to address complex scientific questions.
 - k.* Emphasizing Science Communication and Public Engagement: Enhancing science communication skills among researchers and promoting public engagement with science can help bridge the gap between scientists and the general public, pushing forward a more informed and scientifically literate society.
 - l.* Redesigning Academic Evaluation and Funding Processes: Reevaluating the criteria used to assess researchers and allocate funding can help prioritize long-term impact, innovation, and collaboration over short-term metrics, such as the number of publications or the impact factor of journals.

Rethinking the Foundations of Science

- 49. In this section, we contemplate how alternative approaches to science could reshape our understanding of the natural world and lead to the development of novel theories and models.
- 50. One of the main challenges in conventional science is its reliance on human intuition, which is inherently limited and excludes consideration of phenomena at various scales.
- 51. Throughout history, the development of mathematics and physics has been closely intertwined, with progress in one field often driving advancements in the other.
- 52. This relationship has been critical in shaping our understanding of the universe.

53. However, the emergence of each discipline has been contingent on the specific civilization and context in which it arose.
54. Several alternative mathematical systems, such as non-Euclidean geometry, hypercomplex numbers, and non-classical logics, challenge human intuition and offer new perspectives on the universe.
55. In particular, differential equations are well-suited to describe a continuous world, but in a discrete spacetime, they serve only as approximations.
56. Adopting a quantized view of the universe, with discrete computation as the foundation, could lead to alternative understandings of fundamental physical concepts.
57. Discrete models of physical phenomena would emphasize local rules, discrete states, and step-by-step evolution rather than continuous change.
58. To illustrate, fractal geometry, as the geometrical signature of discrete dynamical systems, offers a rich structure for exploration.
59. In addition, computational paradigms and algorithmic approaches in science align with the quantum nature of our physical world, as demonstrated by quantum computational systems.
60. Considering extraterrestrial civilizations with advanced technology, differences in representation, axiomatic foundations, and interdisciplinary connections could arise due to their unique biology, cognitive abilities, culture, and history.
61. These variations would lead to distinct understandings and developments in physics and mathematics, even if the fundamental laws of the universe remain the same.
62. An alternative scientific approach could involve trial and error, pattern recognition, and adaptation, rather than explicit models, theories, and mathematical reasoning.

63. In this scenario, technology would develop through an iterative, evolutionary process, similar to nature's optimization of biological systems over generations.
64. A neural network-based system serves as an interesting thought experiment to demonstrate the potential of diverse problem-solving strategies.
65. Suppose biology had advanced rapidly before physics.
66. In that case, the scientific landscape and technological progress could have been markedly different, with earlier breakthroughs in medicine, biotechnology, and genetic engineering.
67. Although it is important to recognize the interconnected nature of scientific progress, exploring alternative scenarios can provide valuable insights into the potential of diverse scientific approaches.

Final Remarks

68. Traditional journals combine two functions: publishing and quality control.
69. We propose a disruptive change that separates these roles, preventing the journal from acting as both the publisher and the quality control agency.
70. By adopting self-publication, researchers can transform the way scientific knowledge is disseminated and evaluated, encouraging collaboration, transparency, and accessibility in the process.
71. Self-Publishing Journals (SPJs) bring numerous advantages to researchers and the scientific community.

72. By offering a swifter and more adaptable way for researchers to share their ideas and findings, SPJs support the efficient dissemination of knowledge.
73. Additionally, quality control agencies can appraise and rank SPJs, ensuring that the self-publication model upholds high standards of quality and integrity within the scientific community.
74. In this proposal, we also discussed about a competitive collaboration metric for science that emphasizes both the number of ideas published in scientific journals and the number of co-authors each researcher collaborates with.
75. The iko metric seamlessly integrates the concepts of discretization and collaboration in a straightforward and effective manner.
76. As we envision a future where science operates in novel ways, the integration of open science and self-publishing stands to sustain a collaborative culture, celebrating researchers who actively engage in teamwork and idea-sharing.
77. By championing this approach, we have the potential to nurture a more efficient, accessible, and united scientific community, ultimately propelling the boundaries of innovation and progress to new heights.

AI-Assisted Peer Review Analysis

78. <https://bit.ly/4701Ef1>

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].

Join the **Open Science Collaboration**.

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [6, 7].

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Agreement

The author agrees with [5].

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